

Magnitude and Associated Factors of Alcohol, Cigarette, And Khat Use Among Medical Residents in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, 2023

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ABSTRACT

Background: Substance use, involving alcohol or drugs, impacts all age groups, particularly adolescence and young adults, affecting health, quality of life, and involvement in crime. Over 29 million people worldwide suffer from substance-related disorders, impairing healthcare professionals' skills and potentially compromising patient safety. Therefore, the current study aimed to assess the magnitude of substance use and associated factors among medical residents in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, in 2023.

Methods: A cross-sectional study was conducted among medical residents studying at four hospitals in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia: Yekatit 12 Hospital Medical College, St. Paul's Hospital Millennium Medical College, Tikur Anbessa Specialized Hospital, and Myong Sung Christian Medical Centre. The study included 419 participants, who were selected proportionally from the four hospitals using a stratified sampling method. Descriptive statistics were computed and are presented in tables, graphs, and charts. To identify associated factors, a binary logistic regression model was used; bivariate analysis identified significant variables at p-values ≤ 0.25 , while backward stepwise analysis identified independent associated factors at p-values ≤ 0.05 .

Results: Two hundred eleven (50.4%, 95% CI=45.5%, 55.2%) resident doctors reported a history of substance use. Sex (AOR = 4.54; 95% CI (2.64, 7.80)), living arrangements of residents (living with friends (AOR = 3.92; 95% CI=1.84, 8.39) and living alone (AOR = 2.51; 95% CI=1.44, 4.36)), parental history of substance use (AOR = 2.45; 95% CI=1.29, 4.64), sibling history of substance use (AOR = 3.05; 95% CI=1.67, 5.57), and best friend's history of substance use (AOR = 4.30; 95% CI=2.55, 7.25) were factors significantly associated with substance use history among resident doctors.

Conclusions: This study in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia, found that substance use among medical residents was significantly higher than reported in other studies. Factors including sex, department of residence, living arrangements, and family/peer history of substance use were significantly associated with substance use history. These findings underscore the vulnerability of medical residents to substance use and suggest a potential risk to their professional performance and patient safety. Implementing preventive strategies and support systems tailored to address these specific risk factors is crucial. Additionally, further research is warranted to explore the long-term implications of substance use on medical residents' well-being and their ability to provide quality healthcare in the Ethiopian context.

Key words: Substance use, medical residents, associated factors, cross-sectional study, Ethiopia

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